

MEMORANDUM

To: The Chairman and Members of the Committee on Constitutional, Legal and Parliamentary Affairs

From: Concerned community members

Re: The Promotion of Proper Human Sexual Rights and Ghanaian Family Values Bill, 2021

Date: October 07, 2021

CC: Office of the Attorney-General

1. Introduction

We are a group of concerned community members from within and without Ghana writing to voice our opposition to the proposed Promotion of Proper Human Sexual Rights and Ghanaian Family Values Bill, 2021 being considered in Parliament. If passed, the Bill offends many international treaties that Ghana is a signatory to, including provisions of the United Nations Declaration of Human Rights relating to nondiscrimination. The Bill Will also evidently fuel chaos and the possible loss of lives as a result if attacks based on the hatred towards LGBT+ Ghanians contrary to Resolution 275 of the African Charter on Human and Peoples rights that protects from violence and other Human Rights Violations towards persons on the basis of real or imputed sexual orientation and Gender Identity as well as our own constitutional protections of the sanctity of life. It has also been documented by top Health Agencies including UNAIDS that if passed, the Bill has a high likelihood of undoing all our countries positive strides in fighting the old enemy; HIV/AIDS by sending our affected nationals into hiding. It's upon that background that we invite the honorable team to advise the parliament to consider dropping the Bill due to its far reaching negative implications on all Ghanaians especially country-persons who identify as LGBT+.

2. Petition

In July 2021, we created a petition to voice our concerns about the proposed bill when it was first introduced. Since then, 12,956 people have signed the petition challenging the bill and its attack on LGBTQ+ Ghanaians and over 50 persons have indicated their reasons for

signing, including, "Protecting the human rights of Ghana's LGBTQ citizens is protecting the rights of all Ghanians."

█. Below is the petition language, as well as a link to the page.

"LGBTQ+ Rights in Ghana continue to be threatened by attacks on LGBTQ+ Human Rights Defenders and community. Organisations serving LGBTQ persons have been attacked. LGBTQ persons arrested and detained for weeks as well as public ridicule and religious blackmail including attempts by the clergy to hold "national prayers" against the LGBTQ+ Community In Ghana. Those events culminated in the Draft Legislative submission to the clerk of parliament on 29th/June/2021 titled "Promotion of proper Human Sexual Rights And Ghanaian Family Values Bill 2021" jointly sponsored as a private member's Bill by Member of Parliament for Ningo Pram Pram Honourable, Samuel Nartey George. If the Draft Bill is not rejected and withdrawn, it's highly possible that it will pass by House majority without any challenges and will further endanger lives of Human Rights Defenders and the LGBTIQ+ community in Ghana."

Link:

<https://www.change.org/p/the-government-of-ghana-reject-ghana-s-anti-lgbtq-draft-legislation>